

Exam Protocol

Patient Info:

Name: [REDACTED]

Sex: M ID: P42013

Patient Position: FFS 18-Apr-19 13:10:01

Patient Position: HFS 18-Apr-19 13:14:31

Patient Position: FFS 18-Apr-19 13:14:39

1	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	18-Apr-19 13:48:15
A	97kV 445mA	3.9ms	0.1CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	4888.4 μ Gym ²	158mGy	169LAO 0CRA 397F

5	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	18-Apr-19 14:06:44
A	94kV 289mA	3.8ms	0.1CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	965.65 μ Gym ²	109mGy	169LAO 0CRA 397F

7	3D	FIXED	5sDCT Body Care	4s	60F/s	18-Apr-19 14:16:31
A	94kV 274mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	531.82 μ Gym ²	69.9mGy	168LAO 0CRA 248F

8	3D	FIXED	5sDCT Body Care	4s	60F/s	18-Apr-19 14:30:17
A	94kV 284mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	438.72 μ Gym ²	71.6mGy	168LAO 0CRA 248F

Accumulated exposure data

18-Apr-19 14:37:38

Performing Physician: Fiore

Exposures: 4

Total Fluoro: 00:00:37

Total: 7270.8 μ Gym² 426.3mGyA Fluoro: 00:00:37 446.16 μ Gym² 17.5mGyTotal: 7270.8 μ Gym² 426.3mGy
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